

THE USE OF THE STATUS OF PATIENCE IN THE GHAZALS OF OGAHI

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Abstract. This article discusses the status of patience in Sufi orders. Information is provided about the qualities of the status of patience and its role in Sufism. Also, the interpretations of patience reflected in the ghazals of Ogahiy are analyzed.

Keywords: Order, status, patience, gratitude, contentment

OGAHIY G‘AZALLARIDA SABR MAQOMI ISTIFODASI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada savvuf tariqatlaridagi sabr maqomixususidaso‘zyuritilgan. Sabr maqomining fazilatlarivatasavvufdagio‘rni haqidama’lumotlarkeltirilgan. Shuningdek, Ogahiy g‘azallarida aks etgan sabr talqinlaritahlil qilingan.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается статус терпения в суфийских орденах. Приводится информация о качествах статуса терпения и его роли в суфизме. Также анализируются интерпретации терпения, отраженные в газелях Огахия.

Kalits o‘zlar: Tariqat, maqom, sabr, shukur, qanoat

Ключевые слова: порядок, статус, терпение, благодарность, удовлетворенность

The spiritual destination that leads the *salik* (seeker) to perfection is the station of patience (*sabr*). Patience, for the seeker, signifies steadfastness on the path of trials and hardships, as well as endurance, resilience, and tolerance in times of difficulty and suffering. One of the meanings of the word *sabr* is described as “restraining oneself in moments of hardship” [6,194]. Patience is regarded as one of the noble qualities of the human soul, involving abstention from actions that are not righteous. Professor Ibrohim Haqqul states: “The station of patience in Sufism is also a means of preserving the greatness of the spirit, the purity of the heart, and the freedom of moral character” [4,23]. In the Holy Qur’an, patience is mentioned in more than one hundred verses, and the promises given to those who are patient are true. It is stated: “Say: ‘O My believing servants, fear your Lord. For those who do good in this world, there is goodness. The earth of Allah is vast. Indeed, those who are patient will be given their reward in full, without measure’” [7,197]. Scholars interpret this to mean that the rewards granted to the patient are not calculated individually but are bestowed abundantly and without limit.

Regardless of the stage of the spiritual path, the seeker attains all levels through patience and proper conduct. Professor N. Komilov defines the station of patience as follows: “Patience is endurance and perseverance. In the language of Sufis, it means not complaining about hardships, and especially not appealing to anyone other than God. The patient person (*sobir*) is one who immerses himself in trials and does not fear them” [5,28]. In the hadiths, patience is described as half of faith. This is because patience is a light that strengthens one’s faith, purifies the conscience, and illuminates life. This path is the path of Islam, the path of faith, and the path of truth. For the traveler on the spiritual path, patience serves as a guide—like a caravan leader—leading them toward their ultimate destination. Through this trust, the seeker endures worldly hardships, draws strength from patience, and

ultimately reaches the desired goal. In the ghazals of Ogahiy, the station of patience occupies a special and significant place. In the poet's view, as the lover advances toward spiritual perfection, patience becomes the sole remedy for all the trials and sufferings encountered along the way. He also describes patience as a source of joy and relief. For Ogahiy, patience is the means to attain tranquility and true love:

*There is no remedy for the calamities but to practice patience—
For in this lies the cure of pain and the joy of relief [6,106].*

While the poet regards patience as the balm for all trials written in one's destiny, some scholars describe it as the key to blessings. Abu Bakr Varroq Tirmizi states: "Remaining patient until your spiritual aspiration reaches perfection is the key to all blessings" [1,40].

In Ogahiy's ghazals, two types of patience can be observed: the patience of the common people (*avom*) and the patience of the lover (*oshiq*). The patience of the common people is reflected in endurance in acts of worship, striving for the rewards of paradise, and tolerance toward the events of everyday life. In contrast, the patience of the lover is practiced solely for the sake and pleasure of the Creator. Regardless of the sorrow, hardship, or misfortune encountered, the lover remains patient for the sake of divine union. Addressing the lover, the poet emphasizes that adopting patience as a guiding principle is akin to accepting death itself. One must be prepared to endure suffering and hardship, for the "dagger of patience" may strike the heart at any moment:

*You have made patience your guiding principle—this is no small matter;
If joy and pleasure are replaced by grief and hardship, so be it.*

*Endure with the dagger of patience concealed in your chest—
For death is better than eating bread earned through humiliation [6,31].*

Here, the poet calls for endurance even in poverty and deprivation. The first couplet reflects the patience of the lover, while the second illustrates the patience of the common people.

In another verse, the poet describes how the lover loses patience upon encountering the beloved:

*When that fairy-like beloved entered the gathering, my patience departed;
After drinking wine from the cup, I lost my reason and consciousness [6,86].*

This verse portrays the state of ecstatic love, where the lover becomes overwhelmed. In such cases, patience is directed solely toward the Divine. In another ghazal, the poet expresses that with every passing moment of separation from the beloved, patience diminishes:

*Weep for this sorrow, O eyes, for the beloved departs;
Lament this pain, O heart, for the beloved departs.*

*If I lose patience and composure, it is no fault—
For with every breath, patience and calm depart [6,117].*

In these examples, the poet's Sufi worldview is clearly reflected. Although not all poets can be classified strictly as Sufis, many feel a spiritual closeness to Sufism. As Professor Ibrohim Haqqul notes, belonging to a Sufi path (*tariqa*) involves adhering strictly to its rules under the guidance of a spiritual master, while also encompassing a system of practices and ethical conduct [2,5].

Ultimately, the goal of the seeker on the Sufi path is unity with the Divine. As Abul A'la Afifi observes: "Regardless of its form, the spiritual life of one who journeys toward God constitutes the path (*tariqa*). Whether one belongs to a particular order or follows a specific master is not essential; in this sense, the path is one, for each individual has a unique spiritual world" [2,5]. Concepts such as seclusion (*uzlat*), trust in God (*tavakkul*), poverty and annihilation (*faqr-u fano*), patience (*sabr*), and contentment (*rizo*) expressed in Ogahiy's poetry reflect his distinctive inner spiritual world. According to Professor Ibrohim Haqqul, Ogahiy was less concerned with the formal doctrines and rituals of Sufism; rather, he was drawn to its experiential and emotional dimensions, grounded in love and spiritual attraction [3,181].

The necessity of patience arises from the increasing desire to draw closer to the Creator. As the seeker aspires to attain union with the Truth, they must endure hardships, suffering, and trials with strong willpower. Addressing the heart, the poet urges acceptance of all that comes one's way—whether difficulty, trial, or pain—with patience and gratitude:

Whatever comes before you, O heart, meet it with patience and gratitude, So that God may grant your wishes and ease your hardships [6,241].

In conclusion, the concept of patience occupies a central place in Ogahiy's ghazals as a crucial stage of spiritual perfection. The poet himself regards patience as a guiding principle of life. His portrayal of patience as a source of inner light, a guide toward one's destination, and a remedy for sorrow and suffering clearly confirms its profound significance.

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